

**SPRINKLER IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGY FOR CARROT
CULTIVATION: IMPACT OF PRE-IRRIGATION SOIL MOISTURE AND
RAINFALL INTENSITY ON YIELD**

Burkhonova Munisakhon,

PhD student

*Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers. National Research
University*

E-mail: munisaburxonova1998@gmail.com

Matyakubov Bakhtiyar,

Doctor of Agricultural Sciences, Professor

*Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers. National Research
University*

E-mail: bmatyakubov@inbox.ru

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19433096>

Abstract. *This article explores the effectiveness of sprinkler irrigation technology in carrot cultivation. The study evaluates the impact of various irrigation conditions, including the application of sprinkler irrigation technology, on the yield of the "Mirzoyi qizil" variety. The article discusses the influence of parameters such as pre-irrigation soil moisture, rainfall intensity, and droplet diameter on yield. According to the research results, the highest yield, 29.2 t/ha, was achieved with a pre-irrigation soil moisture of 80-75-60% and a rainfall intensity of 0.4 mm/min. These findings indicate that sprinkler irrigation technology is more efficient than traditional irrigation methods and contributes to increased crop productivity.*

Keywords: *Sprinkler irrigation, carrot cultivation, yield, irrigation technologies, soil moisture, rainfall intensity, droplet diameter, efficiency, agro-technical research.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada sabzi yetishtirishda yomg'irlatib sug'orish texnologiyasining samaradorligi o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotda "Mirzoyi qizil" navini yetishtirishda turli sug'orish sharoitlari, jumladan, yomg'irlatib sug'orish texnologiyasining ta'siri baholangan. Maqolada sug'orish oldi tuproq namligi, yomg'ir jadalligi va tomchi diametri kabi parametrlarning hosildorlikka ta'siri keltirilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, yomg'irlatib sug'orish texnologiyasida sug'orish oldi tuproq namligi 80-75-60% bo'lgan sharoitda va yomg'ir jadalligi 0.4 mm/min bo'lgan variantda sabzining hosildorligi eng yuqori, ya'ni 29,2 t/ga ga yetgan. Bu shuni ko'rsatadiki, yomg'irlatib sug'orish texnologiyasi an'anaviy sug'orish usullariga nisbatan samaraliroq va hosildorlikni oshirishga imkon beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Yomg'irlatib sug'orish, sabzi yetishtirish, hosildorlik, sug'orish texnologiyalari, tuproq namligi, yomg'ir jadalligi, tomchi diametri, samaradorlik, agrotexnik tadqiqotlar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуется эффективность технологии дождевого орошения при выращивании моркови. Оценено влияние различных условий полива, в том числе технологии дождевого орошения, на урожайность сорта «Мирзой кизил». В статье рассмотрены такие параметры, как предполивная влажность почвы, интенсивность дождя и диаметр капли, а также их влияние на урожайность. Результаты исследований показали, что при технологии дождевого орошения наилучший урожай был получен при предполивной влажности почвы 80-75-60% и интенсивности дождя 0,4 мм/мин, который*

OROLBO'YI HUDUDIDA IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA SUV TANQISLIGI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION TEXNIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYALARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik konferensiya

составил 29,2 т/га. Это подтверждает, что технология дождевого орошения более эффективна по сравнению с традиционными методами орошения и позволяет повысить урожайность.

Ключевые слова: Дождевое орошение, выращивание моркови, урожайность, технологии орошения, влажность почвы, интенсивность дождя, диаметр капли, эффективность, агротехнические исследования.

Introduction. Agriculture is the largest consumer of global water resources, which poses serious challenges, particularly in regions experiencing water scarcity [1]. Increasing water-use efficiency, reducing losses, and improving crop productivity require the adoption of water-saving irrigation technologies [2]. One of such technologies is sprinkler irrigation, which has proven to be an effective method of water application. Sprinkler irrigation is an alternative technological approach that simulates the process of natural rainfall during crop irrigation by distributing water across the field in the form of droplets or fine mist, thereby ensuring relatively uniform water application [3]. Compared with conventional surface (gravity-based) irrigation systems, this method can reduce water consumption by up to 50% [4]. In sprinkler irrigation systems, achieving uniform water distribution is crucial for evaluating irrigation engineering efficiency and the uniformity coefficient of the technological processes applied in practice [5].

Studies indicate that combining sprinkler irrigation with minimal or zero tillage practices (no-tillage) may lead to a slight reduction in wheat yield [6]. Nevertheless, this irrigation technology demonstrates high efficiency in water resource utilization and is recognized as an alternative approach capable of ensuring ecological and agronomic sustainability under conditions of water scarcity [6]. Due to their rainfall-like mechanism of water application, sprinkler irrigation systems have been widely used in recent years for various types of crops, including legumes, cereals, and root crops [7, 8]. The technology was initially introduced for rice cultivation in the Sardinia region of Italy and was later applied to many rice varieties. When compared with the traditional continuous flooding irrigation method, it demonstrated nearly similar yield performance. This confirms that sprinkler irrigation technology is not only a water-saving method but also a technique capable of maintaining high crop productivity.

Materials and Methods. Laboratory and field trials were conducted in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the following methodologies: "Methodology for Conducting Experiments in Vegetable, Root, and Potato Cultivation" [9], "Practical Training in Vegetable Crop Breeding, Seed Production,

and Seed Science" [10], "Vegetable Crop Breeding and Seed Production" [11], "Practical Training in Vegetable Cultivation" [12], "Carrot Cultivation" [13], as well as the guidelines developed by the Irrigation and Water Problems Scientific Research Institute and the "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers" National Research University.

Field experiments were conducted during the 2023-2024 growing seasons to evaluate the effectiveness of sprinkler irrigation for carrot cultivation (variety "Mirzoyi qizil"). Four irrigation variants were tested: furrow irrigation (control) and three sprinkler irrigation variants with varying pre-irrigation soil moisture levels (80-75-60%) and rainfall intensities (0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 mm/min). Soil moisture was measured as a percentage relative to field capacity (RFC), and the sprinkler system used was the **S-10 Mini Sprinkler** with a nozzle size of 2.8 mm, providing controlled rainfall intensities. Carrot yield was recorded in tonnes per hectare (t/ha) at harvest, and the effect of different irrigation methods on yield was analyzed. Statistical methods were used to evaluate the results and identify the optimal irrigation conditions for better productivity.

Research Results.

3.1. Carrot Sprinkler Irrigation

In the study, the S-10 Mini sprinkler model was used, which is distinguished by its low water consumption and specially designed wing and nozzle system. This design helps to prevent excessive water accumulation on the soil surface, which can lead to the formation of a hard crust. The device is capable of distributing water uniformly over a circular area, up to a distance of 6 meters, ensuring a high degree of homogeneity in water application (Figure 1).

Figure 1. S-10 Mini Sprinkler Irrigation Device and Its Operating Process

The S-10 Mini model is designed for harsh operating conditions, with its key structural elements made from high-strength plastic and stainless steel materials. The device's materials exhibit high resistance to chemical reagents, ultraviolet radiation, and mechanical impacts, ensuring its long-lasting durability.

The S-10 Mini sprinkler is distinguished by its ability to distribute water evenly, its resistance to atmospheric influences, and its construction reliability. These features make it highly suitable for efficient use in agricultural irrigation systems.

Nozzle (Sprayer) Design and Operational Characteristics

One of the key advantages of the nozzle assortment is the availability of various nozzle options that are tailored to meet different water consumption requirements. This variety enables optimization of hydraulic calculations in the design, allows for the customization of spray characteristics, and helps achieve maximum efficiency for specific irrigation systems. The wide range of nozzle configurations provides flexibility in the design process, ensuring high technical reliability and operational convenience in various conditions (Figure 2, Table 1).

Figure 2. Types of Nozzles (Sprayers) for the S-10 Mini Sprinkler

Table 1.

Operating Range of the S-10 Mini Sprinkler with 2.8 × 1.8mm Nozzle

Pressure (Bar)	Water flow (l/h)	Nozzle Spray Distribution Diameter (m)
2,5	740	11
3,0	802	12
3,5	898	13

The improvements mentioned above enhance the efficiency of sprinkler irrigation in accordance with the agro-technical requirements of carrots, ensuring better water use efficiency and contributing to the development of an environmentally sustainable technology.

OROLBO'YI HUDUDIDA IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA SUV TANQISLIGI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION TEXNIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYALARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik konferensiya

When evaluating the effectiveness of sprinkler irrigation technology, the droplet diameter is one of the key hydraulic indicators. The droplet size directly affects plant leaf surface damage, soil structure, water infiltration rate, and erosion processes. Therefore, in this study, the droplet diameter for the S-10 Mini Sprinkler was determined based on the empirical model proposed by Kostiakov, Christiansen, and other researchers.

To calculate the droplet diameter, the following empirical formula was applied:

$$d = k \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{Q}{P}}$$

where:

d is the droplet diameter, in mm;

Q is the sprinkler water flow rate, in cm³/s;

P is the working pressure, in bar;

k is the empirical coefficient (based on experiments, $k=0.62$ is assumed).

The water flow rate values were converted into cm³/s units for calculating the droplet diameter.

Calculation under 2.5 Bar Pressure

$$Q = \frac{740000}{3600} = 205.5 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$$

$$d = 0.62 \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{205.5}{2.5}} = 2.69 \text{ mm}$$

Calculation under 3.0 Bar Pressure

$$Q = \frac{802000}{3600} = 222.8 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$$

$$d = 0.62 \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{222.8}{3}} = 2.60 \text{ mm}$$

Calculation under 3.5 Bar Pressure

$$Q = \frac{898000}{3600} = 249.4 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$$

$$d = 0.62 \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{249.4}{3.5}} = 2.55 \text{ mm}$$

It can be observed from the calculations that as the pressure in the sprinkler increases, the droplet diameter decreases. This aligns with the physical law, where higher pressure causes the water to break into finer dispersed droplets. The droplet diameter formed by the S-10 Mini Sprinkler nozzle ranged from 2.55 to 2.69 mm (Table 2).

OROLBO'YI HUDUDIDA IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA SUV TANQISLIGI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION TEXNIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYALARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik konferensiya

Table 2.

Relationship Between Droplet Diameter and Pressure

Pressure (bar)	Calculated Droplet Diameter (mm)
2.5	2.69 mm
3.0	2.60 mm
3.5	2.55 mm

According to the research findings, when the working pressure is 2.5 bar, the water flow rate is 740 l/h, the rainfall intensity is 0.3 mm/min, and the droplet diameter is 2.69 mm (table 3). As the pressure increases to 3.0 bar, the water flow rate rises to 802 l/h, the rainfall intensity increases to 0.4 mm/min, and the droplet diameter decreases to 2.60 mm. At a pressure of 3.5 bar, the water flow reaches 898 l/h, the rainfall intensity increases to 0.5 mm/min, and the droplet diameter decreases further to 2.55 mm.

Table 3

S-10 Mini Sprinkler (Nozzle Size 2.8 mm)

Pressure (bar)	2.5	3.0	3.5
Average Water Flow (l/h)	740	802	898
Rainfall Intensity (mm/min)	0,3	0,4	0,5
Droplet Diameter (mm)	2,69	2,60	2,55

The data obtained indicate that the variant with a rainfall intensity of 0.4 mm/min is the most optimal, as in this regime, water infiltration into the soil occurred steadily, and no compaction or erosion of the soil surface was observed. Furthermore, the average droplet diameter ensured uniform water distribution, creating a favorable water-air regime for the normal development of carrot roots.

In sprinkler irrigation technology, achieving efficiency depends heavily on technical parameters such as rainfall intensity, droplet size, and uniform water distribution. These parameters must ensure that plants remain undamaged, soil structure is preserved, and water is utilized to its maximum potential.

According to the research results, the following working parameters of the S-10 Mini Sprinkler model were found to be optimal:

The working pressure is 3.0 bar;

The sprinkler water flow rate is 802 l/h, ensuring uniform irrigation;

The rainfall intensity is 0.4 mm/min, which corresponds to the soil's water infiltration capacity;

The droplet diameter is 2.60 mm, which is of average size and prevents the formation of a crust on the soil surface;

Water infiltrates into the layer where the roots are located without running off the soil surface;

OROLBO‘YI HUDUDIDA IQLIM O‘ZGARISHI VA SUV TANQISLIGI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION TEXNIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYALARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik konferensiya

The soil's water-air regime is maintained in a stable condition;
Favorable conditions are created for the development of carrot roots;
Irrigation water efficiency is improved, and water losses are minimized.

These results highlight the advantages of using the S-10 Mini Sprinkler under these conditions, ensuring optimal water distribution and efficient irrigation while preserving soil health and promoting healthy crop growth.

3.2. Effect of Sprinkler Irrigation on Carrot Yield

The analysis of average carrot yield in the 2023-2024 field experiments on the cultivation of the "Mirzoyi qizil" variety using sprinkler irrigation technology is presented below. According to the research results, in the control variant where furrow irrigation was applied, the average yield was 22.7 t/ha. In all variants using sprinkler irrigation technology, the yield performance was higher compared to the control group (Table 4). In particular, the highest average yield of 29.2 t/ha was recorded in Variant 3, where pre-irrigation soil moisture was 80-75-60% relative to the field capacity (CHDNS), and the rainfall intensity was 0.4 mm/min. This result was significantly higher than the furrow-irrigated control variant, making Variant 3 the most optimal and effective under sprinkler irrigation conditions.

The experimental results indicate that when sprinkler irrigation technology is applied, the yield from the field is higher compared to traditional furrow irrigation methods. The main reasons for the increased yield include the timely and direct delivery of water and nutrients to the plant root zone, reduced soil compaction due to less mechanical intervention in the field compared to furrow-irrigated variants, and improved root system growth and development of the carrots.

Table 4.

Effect of Pre-Irrigation Soil Moisture and Rainfall Intensity on Carrot Yield (Average, 2023-2025)

Options	Irrigation Technology	Pre-irrigation soil moisture relative to the Field Capacity (CHDNS), %	Rainfall Intensity (mm/min)	Average Yield, (t/ha)
1	Furrow Irrigation	(Control)		22,7
2	Sprinkler Irrigation	80-75-60	0,3	27,8
3			0,4	29,2
4			0,5	27,7

The results of this study demonstrated the effectiveness of sprinkler irrigation technology in carrot cultivation. Sprinkler irrigation significantly increased yield

OROLBO‘YI HUDUDIDA IQLIM O‘ZGARISHI VA SUV TANQISLIGI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION TEXNIKA VA TEXNOLOGIYALARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik konferensiya

compared to traditional furrow irrigation, with the highest yield observed under pre-irrigation soil moisture of 80-75-60% and a rainfall intensity of 0.4 mm/min. This condition ensured optimal root development, stable soil water-air balance, and enhanced water use efficiency. To improve the efficiency of sprinkler irrigation, it is essential to maintain optimal pre-irrigation soil moisture and rainfall intensity. Expanding the use of sprinkler irrigation, especially in water-scarce regions, is highly beneficial. Further optimization of irrigation regimes and the expansion of experimental fields will enhance system effectiveness. Modernizing and automating irrigation system management will significantly improve water use efficiency.

References:

1. Ingraio C. et al. Water scarcity in agriculture: An overview of causes, impacts and approaches for reducing the risks // *Heliyon*. 2023. Vol. 9, № 8. P. 15.
2. Jaramillo Valencia A. Adoption of Water-Saving Technologies in Agriculture // *Agriculture and Water Management Under Climate Change* / ed. Çetin Ö. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024. P. 29–47.
3. Sidhu R.K. et al. Automation in drip irrigation for enhancing water use efficiency in cereal systems of South Asia: Status and prospects // *Advances in Agronomy*. Elsevier, 2021. Vol. 167. P. 247–300.
4. Al-Dosary N.M.N. et al. Employing Data Mining Algorithms and Mathematical Empirical Models for Predicting Wind Drift and Evaporation Losses of a Sprinkler Irrigation Method // *Water (Switzerland)*. MDPI, 2023. Vol. 15, № 5. P.14
5. Hui X. et al. A simplified method to improve water distribution and application uniformity for sprinkler irrigation on sloping land: Adjustment of riser orientation // *Water Supply*. IWA Publishing, 2021. Vol. 21, № 6. P. 13.
6. Odhafa A.K.H., Lahmod N.R., Hassan A.K.H. Evaluation of Tillage Systems on Wheat Crop Production Under Surface and Sprinkler Irrigation Methods: Application for Rural Areas Close to Baghdad, Iraq // *Air, Soil and Water Research*. SAGE Publications Ltd, 2022. Vol. 15. P.10.
7. Alberto Ma.C.R. et al. Carbon uptake and water productivity for dry-seeded rice and hybrid maize grown with overhead sprinkler irrigation // *Field Crops Res*. 2013. Vol. 146. P. 51–65.
8. Jagosz B. et al. Effect of sprinkler irrigation on yield increasing of carrot roots obtained in cultivation on light soil in different regions of Poland. 2019. P.6
9. Crop Water and Irrigation Requirements Program of FAO (CROPWAT), <http://www.fao.org/land-water/land/land-governance/land-resources-planning-toolbox/category/details/en/c/1026559/>. 2018, 20-28 b.
10. Azimov, B.J., Azimov, B.B. “Methodology for Conducting Experiments in Vegetable, Root, and Potato Cultivation” // *Uzbekistan National Encyclopedia*, State National Publishing House. Tashkent – 2002, pp. 25–31.
11. Bo‘riyev, H.Ch., Zuyev, V.I., Qodirxo‘jayev, O.Q. “Practical Training in Vegetable Crop Breeding, Seed Production, and Seed Science” // *Textbook*. 1997, pp. 56–59.
12. Bo‘riyev, H.Ch. “Vegetable Crop Breeding and Seed Production” // Tashkent: *Mehnat*, 1999, pp. 16–24.
13. G‘afurova, F., Qodirozov, R. “Practical Training in Vegetable Cultivation” // Tashkent: *O‘qituvchi*, 1983, pp. 41–45.